

S P Λ T I A L

Branding guidelines

Elements & rules - 2021

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01

Logos

Logos declinations &
rules

Logo on white background

This logo is to be used on white and lightly colored backgrounds.
It must not be used on blue or green backgrounds.
Pick the format based on your needs.

Logo on blue background

This logo is to be used on blue and dark colored backgrounds.
It must not be used on white or green backgrounds.
Pick the format based on your needs.

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Logo on green background

This logo is to be used on green backgrounds.
It must not be used on blue or white background.
Pick the format based on your needs.

02

Color Palette

Color codes & uses

Color Palette

These are the main colors to be used.
You can use them either in with full saturation or
at any lower level of saturation.
#042464 Should have the priority for longer texts
and smaller ones.

03

Typography

Fonts & how to use them

Titles

Open Sans Bold/Extrabold

**Abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890**

Download [here](#)

Main Texts

Lato Light/Regular

Abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Download [here](#)

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Thank you

MORE INFO

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